

The ethical significance of exemplifying: A response to Anthony Essien

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In his plenary paper, Tony Essien wrote that “The importance of mathematical examples [...] cannot be overemphasised”. Tony’s paper opened my eyes to the significance of examples and of the complex practice of exemplifying in multilingual mathematics education in general, and in teacher education in particular. The triadic framework that Tony proposed captures exemplifying as illustrating concepts from the perspectives of (a) grasping the illustrated concept by discernment; (b) communicating about the illustration as a fundamental idea of teaching and learning; and (c) attending to the multilingual context (of pre-service teachers) in which the illustration is submerged.

Multilingualism in mathematics education

Before moving further, I would like to recognise that multilingual pre-service teachers and multilingual students in general are far from a homogeneous group either in, or across contexts (Barwell, 2016; Civil, 2012). However, multilingual students are often from marginalised groups whose opportunities to learn mathematics are diminished compared to their peers from majority/dominant groups whose first language is the language of power and hegemony and of learning and teaching (e.g., Chronaki, 2009; Källberg, 2018). I consider a multilingual classroom to be any classroom where more than one language is present. Hence, some students in a multilingual classroom may be multilingual, while others are not.

In multilingual classrooms some languages might be silenced due to monolingual norms and/or policies, but they are silently present in every instance of the interaction (García & Wei, 2014). Different languages in which different experiences, knowledges and worldviews are embedded (Knijnik, 2012; Radford, 2012) are brought into the learning spaces. This means that students may experience non-hegemonic and hegemonic cultural and language resources against each other at school, often finding some of their cultural, epistemological, and language resources and identities ignored or perhaps even rejected. Ultimately, this may influence multilingual students’ future prospects. Therefore, multilingualism in mathematics classrooms is a matter of social, political, cultural, and ethical issues.

Ethical dimensions of a ‘good’ example

Initially, Tony shared some questions that inspired him to conduct research about the practice of exemplifying in multilingual mathematics teacher education. One such question

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was: “What should a “good” (use of) example be in multilingual pre-service teacher education mathematics classrooms?” This question invited me to consider value-laden or ethical dimensions of the practice of exemplifying in multilingual learning spaces. Indeed, the word example can be used to express conducts of behaviour; an example is one that/who serves as a desired pattern to be imitated – a role model. An example may also be a punishment inflicted on someone as a warning to others (Merriam-Webster Thesaurus Online, n.d.).

The philosophical branch of ethics is concerned with questions of right or wrong, of benevolence and harm, and about what is proper conduct. Ethics is not a monolithic concept. Rather, it covers a broad range of ideas that span from normative, utilitarian conceptions of virtue and duty, to postmodern ethics that embrace dimensions that may capture the ecological, the social and cultural, others, and self (Dubbs, 2020). Skovsmose (2020) suggested that adding an ethical dimension to mathematics opens up a space for reflection on the ways in which mathematical activity impacts upon society. He suggested that critical mathematics education offers the capacity to embrace such ethical reflection.

Opening up a space for ethical reflection

The triadic framework that Tony proposed helped me to identify one instance in the excerpt that he provided that has the potential to open up a space for ethical reflection on political effects of monolingual mathematics education in multilingual societies. In line 14 of the excerpt, a pre-service teacher softly replied “Unlikely” when the teacher asked what the chances of “winning” are when tossing a coin. It appears as if the coin-tossing example allowed the pre-service teacher who replied “Unlikely” to discern some critical aspects that relates to injustice. There ought to be equal opportunities that the heads or the tails appear when the coin is tossed, and the chances of winning should be 50 percent. The “unlikely” reply may be a reply that challenges the idea of equal opportunities. It could suggest a disadvantaged position where chances in life and opportunities, such as learning mathematics, are unequally distributed. In the interaction, the “Unlikely” reply seems to pass unnoticed by the teacher and by the other pre-service teachers because no one comments on it. The “Unlikely” reply could provide an opportunity to open up a space for reflection on the ways in which mathematical (school) activity impacts upon societies that are multilingual, which most societies are. In this space, reflections may capture and move forward a critique in multilingual mathematics education that revolve around discourses such as those discussed by Chronaki and Planas (2018) regarding representation and politics, language as resource, Eurocentrism, racism and epistemic violence, deficits, benevolence, dichotomies (formal-informal mathematics, first–second language, global-local, foregrounds-backgrounds) and othering, *et cetera*. These are discourses that pre-service teachers need to navigate as they are at once “enculturated into becoming teachers of mathematics, becoming teachers of mathematics in multilingual classrooms, becoming learners of mathematics content, becoming learners of mathematical practices and becoming proficient LoLT users for the purpose of teaching/learning mathematics” (Essien, 2021, in this volume, p. 45).

A relational perspective on ethics

What are good examples of how to navigate such spaces? How do we deal with the idea that, for instance, a 50–50 chance of “winning” might be true for some students in some situations, while winning might be very “unlikely” for other students, without reproducing stigmatising categorizations or deficit discourses (Norén & Boistrup, 2013)? Or without putting an extra burden on marginalised groups, demanding that they explain or share their experiences (Hand et al., 2021)?

The questions invite me to consider Swanson’s (2017) writings:

Perhaps it is time for us to remember what the intentions of mathematics education should be, to live well with mathematics education in order to live well with others; to live and research well with mathematics education in order to make possible futures of radical hope. (Swanson, 2017, p. 13)

The above quote shifts the attention from an ethical reflection on how mathematical activity may impact upon society to how we (for example educators and pre-service teachers) inhabit mathematics learning spaces in ways that allow us to live well with mathematics and with each other. In other words, the attention shifts from socio-political projects to a critique that centres considerations in multilingual mathematics activities from a relational perspective of ethics.

Swanson (2017) reminded me that for us to live well with mathematics, mathematics education and research, we may need to expand theories of ethics from non-Euro-centred perspectives. She called for a move towards, for example, indigenous, decolonial, posthuman ontologies, epistemologies, and theories to live better with each other as we engage mathematics. Drawing on indigenous knowledges (Ermine, 2007), Russell and Chernoff (2013) proposed ethics as a capacity and/or will to know what may harm or enhance ecological, social, and cultural well-being, and the well-being of others and self. While it may be challenging to grow a capacity to know what may harm or enhance the well-being of multilingual pre-service teachers or multilingual students in mathematics learning spaces, it is crucial.

Closing remarks

The triadic framework that Tony presented concurrently captures the significance of ensuring access to dominant mathematics for multilingual pre-service teachers *and* the significance of highlighting the presence of language and thereby also cultural and epistemological diversity, in exemplifying practices as part of language diverse learning spaces. In other words, the framework allows us to move away from dichotomising stands that revolves around either-or issues such as knowing and learning dominant vs non-dominant languages and/or mathematics. The capacity to recognise the socio-political significance of multilingual pre-service teachers and students getting access to dominant mathematics and dominant languages may be a matter of enhancing well-being. It could provide multilingual pre-service teachers with the language and mathematical resources

they need in order to be heard and listened to by others such as parents, students, and colleagues. However, without pausing for ethical reflection and critique (Hand et al., 2021), dominant languages and mathematics will simply be (re)produced, which could potentially cause harm (Le Roux & Rughubar-Reddy, 2021).

For example, ethical reflection could comprise illuminating the significance of the presence of non-dominant languages and mathematics in multilingual learning spaces. A both-and stand – that is, a stand that embraces both dominant languages and mathematics and non-dominant languages and mathematics, which I believe Tony’s triadic framework does – is a good example that could help us inhabit mathematics learning spaces in ways that allow us to live well, or at least a little bit better with mathematics and with each other.

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